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Combined 2D animation in television series

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[Animação / Animation]

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Abstract

In the animation industry, there are always three parameters: cost, time and visual style. All are important, although at the audience level, only the visual is seen. The last 30 years, thanks to technological advances, have made it possible to optimize the processes of the 2D animated series for television. The increase in platforms, demands more animated content, and for that series to stand out, it must be visually original. To look for this premise, the studios are looking for ways to create a series with a visual style that is different from the rest, but that does not affect production times and does not increase costs, because it would no longer be profitable. What is beginning to be achieved is to mix flat animation techniques, with the more traditional techniques of 2D, but updated to the digital age. Analyzed three series, with different visual style, the guidelines achieved on the visual results of each one of them are shown.

1. Introduction

At present, we have different media and audiovisual platforms. Different animation series, either by theme or by visual style.

Thinking about the productions of 30 years ago, the series was based on successful styles like those of Hanna Barbera². One of the principles for one of the animated series to approach success is to make it original, a visual style different from the rest, think of *Amazing world of Gumball*, *Adventure Time* or *Steve Universe*³. The visual style has to be one of the important factors at the time of creation, but influenced by production costs and times. The analysis should take into account the value of production, exploring manuals, resources and interviews, highlighting the person of Belli Ramírez, recognized production manager at European level. This analysis is done by focusing on the animated production of series from the occidental perspective, since the processes of Asia, and specifically Japan, follow other processes⁴.

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² Hanna-Barbera Productions was formed in 1957 by William Hanna and Joseph Barbera, who had been partners in animation at MGM Studios where they created the memorable Tom and Jerry shorts. They left MGM when the studio stopped production on animated films. Hanna and Barbera achieved immediate success on television with *The Huckleberry Hound Show* in 1958, followed later by the highly popular prime-time series, *The Flintstones*. Through the next thirty years, Hanna-Barbera produced an astonishing 249 individual cartoon series for television—totaling over 1,200 hours of original episodes.

³ Cartoon Network animation channel series.

⁴ PhD thesis. HORNO LÓPEZ, Antonio (2013). *Animación japonesa. Análisis de series de anime actuales*. Granada, Universidad de Granada.

In recent years, new animation processes have been created, thanks to advances in digital applications. The 2D animation for series has been completely digitized, as it allows the studios to reduce costs and production times. These processes, which have updated traditional systems to digital, are opening up options in the visual aspect of the series, leaving aside overexploited styles.

In this case, we are talking about two processes, one is the digital cut-out, where the animators have all the parts of the character, and animate it as if it were a puppet, which is why it is also called *Puppets Animation*. The other process is traditional animation, but instead of using paper, pencil, acetate⁵,... an application is used, where you can draw and generate the number of frames needed for the sequence. It is also called *Tradigital or Paperless*.

This study shows the starting point by analyzing three 2D animated series, where emphasis is placed on the technical process, mixing the two processes in order to make a series, with fewer limitations in its visual finish, which affects the work of the animator who facilitates the production process, and thus does not increase the time and costs of production.

These processes complement each other, and are increasingly being implemented in the studios, as they allow us to obtain a series with a unique, unique and more elaborate visual finish.

2. Methods

In order to carry out this study, a number of animated series were analyzed, which were accessible to the production processes. Not only the viewing of chapters, but also the access to the material of the production, where it is possible to visualize the techniques and resources used in the projects. Three series issued internationally have been selected to show the relevance of this study.

With the material obtained, we searched for the use of the traditional digital animation process and the puppet system. This analysis provides a hybrid process of the commented animation processes, showing that it is possible to extrapolate it to other productions.

3. Results

After the analysis of the series from the available material, it is shown that the animation studios look for, to facilitate the work of the animator, improving the production times. One of the problems of animated series is to maintain the visual style throughout their episodes. One of the weak points of a character, to maintain the style, is the design of his head, gestures,... the job of the animator is to draw the character as close to the original design in each shot, which slows down the production times of a series made with the traditional digital process.

The Puppets animation system can be unlimitedly repetitive in the poses and actions that the character animators must perform, affecting the pre-production process in the design of the characters and their visual finish.

⁵ Laybourne, Kit,.. The animation Book.: Line and Cel animation. pp. 171--215. Three River Press, New York (1998).

Fig. 2. Rough animation in Motor City.

Fig. 3. Library of the head of character for Motor City.

rest of the characters' bodies are animated in a traditional way, i.e. drawn. Therefore, the head piece has enough nested material in itself to make the sequence and expression that the character needs in the plane. The animator in this way makes the drawings of the poses that the character needs, and with respect to the head must use the material nestled in the head piece, selecting the frames that are necessary for the movement of that part. At the same time, it also gives the expression of the face of the protagonist. In this way, a visual unity is achieved between episodes, in the heads and faces of the characters, and in turn an optimization in the work of the animator.

Fig. 4. Rough animation in Amazing world of Gumball.

Fig. 5. Rough animation in Amazing world of Gumball.

In the **Amazing world of Gumball** series, with a much more cartoon aesthetic, the characters are developed with all the pre-production material, head poses, hands, eyes, mouths, among others. In this series the main animators, have the reference of all the elements that compose the characters, but they are the ones who decide if they use it or draw again based on all this material. In the production process of this series, the plan cleaning team is in charge of making use of the material already generated in pre-production, since it speeds up production times. With this system it allows them to maintain the visual entity of the series, keeping the design of the main characters perfectly the same in each episode. The third series analyzed is **Niko and the Sword of Light**⁹. In the material analyzed again we see the heads with a finished animation while the rest of

Fig. 6. Rough animation in Niko and the Sword of light.

Fig. 7. Rough animation in Niko and the Sword of light.

⁹ Animated series by Titmouse studio, for Amazon Prime. 2017.

the body is drawn in undefined, non-colored strokes, just like in Motor City. In this series the aesthetics used are more cartoon. This series has action scenes which need solid drawings to highlight the sequence, which would not have enough emphasis with the production process of Puppets, which would force to generate the most complex character, with more pieces, when the drawn animation process allows a greater freedom of drawing poses, and getting a silhouette¹⁰ that allows to have a solid drawing.

4. Conclusion

In the 2D animated series of the 1990s, you could see the same character between episodes and sometimes between chapters, which did not look so much like the original design, that they were not a model, as they say in the industry. The most noticeable was in the heads, faces and lip-synchronization, and this did not please a professional audience. The causes can be various, corresponding to the first episodes, and even the animators do not have enough drawing practice of the characters, or different levels of the cartoonists.

The mixture of the traditional digital technique together with the animation of puppets, allows us to produce more accurate visuals, and a technical development in the creation of the characters. This allows for better results, which is what the industry is looking for.

The following figure¹¹ shows a comparison between the two techniques from the point of view of the animation process. As we can see, there is a difference in the human team involved, but we must also take into account the execution times, which we can see in figures 9 and 10¹². These two elements with the visual element, which makes the series unique and different, show the basics of animated production.

Fig. 8. Comparative graphic of the animation staff team between a traditional 2D project and another 2D puppets.

The animation studio must work on a more exhaustive pre-production of the characters, defining well the parts that are going to be used as the character's library, such as the rotation of the head, blinking or lip-sync among others. This greater control means that small animations have to

¹⁰ Clarity is the key ingredient when creating your silhouettes. Understand and draw the forms before you commit to just random blobs. Your goal is organization. Silver, Stephen.: The Silver Way, techniques, tips and tutorials for Effective Character Design. pp. 77. Design Studio Press (2017).

¹¹ CORSARO, Sandro, J. PARROTT, Clifford (2004). Hollywood 2D, digital animation. Course Technology PTR.

¹² From the source at <http://mrcohl.com> by Belli Ramirez, production management in animation projects with more than 25 years in the industry.

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